

PREVALENCE AND PATTERNS OF ALLERGIES IN THE STUDENT POPULATION OF PESHAWAR: A CROSS-SECTIONAL ANALYSIS.

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Abstract

Background: Allergies, which are a significant global health concern, are caused by an inappropriate immune system's response to various ecological (environmental, dietary, and drug-related) allergens. Despite the rapidly rising allergic diseases all around the globe, limited data exist on their frequency among Pakistan's youth and especially Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Objective:

1. To determine the frequency and types of allergies among students of Peshawar University.
2. To explore the association of allergies with gender and family history among students of Peshawar University.

Materials and Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 425 students, aged 15 to 28 years. Participants were selected using Cochran's formula for sample size determination. Data were collected through structured questionnaires distributed in printed and digital formats. The association between allergies, gender, and family history was analysed using chi-square tests. P-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:

In self-reported allergies, dust allergy was the most commonly reported (60.78% in females vs. 52.79% in males, $p = 0.08$), followed by allergic rhinitis and allergic conjunctivitis. Seasonal allergy ($p = 0.04$) and contact dermatitis ($p = 0.041$) were significantly more common among females, whereas pollen allergy was more frequently reported by males (28.93% vs. 18.97%, $p = 0.01$). Among the 177 participants who reported physician-diagnosed allergies, the most frequent conditions were dust mite allergy (28.2%), allergic rhinitis (15.8%), and atopic dermatitis (12.4%). Cosmetic allergy and atopic dermatitis were significantly more common in females ($p < 0.001$ and $p = 0.037$, respectively).

Regarding family history, 240 participants (55.71%) reported a positive family history of allergies. Allergic conjunctivitis had the highest familial

association and was significantly more common in females (23.7%) than males (17%) ($p = 0.01$). Similarly, pollen allergy was more often reported in females (5% vs. 2.0%, $p = 0.04$). No significant gender differences were observed in the family history of other allergy types.

Conclusion: The study highlights the high prevalence of various allergies among Peshawar University students, with significant associations with gender and family history. Targeted awareness programs, preventive measures, and allergen management strategies are recommended to improve student health and academic outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Allergies are caused by the immune system's aberrant reaction to allergens. An environmental chemical that is often innocuous causes the immune system to respond. Allergens are a class of substances that include pollen, mold, dust, animal dander, some foods, bugs, and more. A category of immune-mediated illnesses known as allergic diseases has a high prevalence globally, involving 30% of the overall population, and their incidence is sharply rising [1].

Each form of allergy is brought on by a distinct allergen. Such as dermatitis brought on by cosmetics and home chemicals, pet allergies, dust mite allergies, food allergies, pollen allergies, pet allergies, and allergies to mold and pollen.

The majority of particulate matter particles lie in the 20 μ m to 60 μ m range in size, and pollen as an aeroallergen typically contains protein molecules with molecular weights between 10,000 and 40,000 Da. Most of the particles from the environment didn't reach the alveoli due to protective mechanisms in the respiratory tract, except particles having a size of 5 μ m or less it which evade the normal defence mechanisms [2].

Allergy to animals is the second most prevalent form. It appears to be nearly impossible to remove every single hair with a fuzz scraper, making it a laborious task. There is a considerable increase in dog and cat allergens in settings where there are no animals, such as houses, schools, nurseries, and workplaces. This has led to a rise in the occurrence of allergies to these animals [3]. Almost all furred animals will cause allergy responses when exposed on frequently. The results of an epidemiologic research conducted in Japan on 5000 lab animals including mice, rats, rabbits, pigs, monkeys and many more showed that the following percentages of animals experienced

allergic symptoms among all those exposed: 26% of mice, 25% of rats, 31% of guinea pigs, 30% of rabbits, 26% of hamsters, 25% of dogs, 30% of cats, and 24% of monkeys [4]. The one that follows them in frequency is food allergies. Food allergies can be defined as "an unfavorable health consequence emerging from a particular immune response that takes place robustly upon exposure to a certain meal." Allergens include the "Big 8," or milk, fish, crustacean shellfish, milk, tree nuts, wheat, peanuts and soybeans. These eight allergens are thought to cause 90% of food allergy reactions. Immunoglobulin E (IgE) mediated food allergy is a major public health issue that affects 8% of children and between 3 and 10% of adults worldwide [5]. After food the abundant one is mold allergy (a general term for fungus, mushrooms, etc.). IgE-mediated allergic rhinitis, asthma and dermatitis can all be brought on by exposure to allergenic molds, and it has been shown that the severity of an asthmatic arrest is correlated with sensitivity to certain fungi like *Aspergillus* and/or *Alternaria*. Mold allergies are thought to affect 3 to 10% of the population [6]. The next typical allergy is brought on by dust mites. The house dust mite (HDM) is a substantial source of allergens that are present year-round and is a key contributor to allergic rhinitis and allergic asthma. Data on the prevalence of HDM allergen sensitivity ranges from 65 to 130 million people globally, to up to 50% among asthmatic patients [7]. Patients can occasionally be allergic to common household chemicals and cosmetics. The prevalent dermatologic complaint of contact dermatitis brought on by cosmetic items has a significant negative impact on the patient's overall quality. This condition accounts for between 2% and 4% of all dermatologist consultations, with

approximately 60% of cases being allergic. The most common causes among these are cosmetic nail and hair products, next to skin care and moisturizing products. The most frequent cause of allergies to cosmetics is fragrance, followed by hair dyes and preservatives [8].

Despite the growing burden of allergies worldwide, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, there is a lack of localized data on the prevalence and patterns of these conditions. Allergies are often underdiagnosed and underestimated in community settings, leading to insufficient preventive strategies and delayed interventions. In many parts of the world, including Pakistan, allergic disorders remain poorly documented in terms of distribution by type, age, gender, and environmental exposure. This lack of epidemiological insight limits healthcare providers' ability to plan effective awareness, screening, and treatment programs tailored to local needs. Understanding the prevalence and types of allergies in a specific population is essential for developing targeted public health strategies and clinical interventions. With increasing environmental pollution, lifestyle changes, and urbanization, allergic conditions are becoming more common, yet data remains scarce, particularly in regional and student populations. By documenting the distribution and frequency of common allergies, this study aims to fill a critical knowledge gap. The findings will not only inform local healthcare providers and policymakers but also serve as a foundation for educational campaigns and preventive strategies aimed at reducing the burden of allergic diseases.

Objectives:

1. To find out the frequency of different types of allergies among students in the University of Peshawar.
2. To assess the association of allergies with gender and family history.

Materials and Methods: Study design, Settings, and duration:

This cross-sectional study was conducted within the University of Peshawar (UOP) campus and included several affiliated institutions situated within its boundaries. The selected settings comprised the

Home Economics College (UOP), Agriculture University Peshawar, Islamia College University Peshawar, Khyber Medical College (UOP), and Jinnah College for Women (UOP). The data collection was carried out over a defined period of 3 months.

Sample size:

The sample size was calculated using Cochran's formula: $n = Z^2 \cdot p \cdot q / e^2$, where Z is the standard normal value at a 95% confidence level (1.96), p is the estimated prevalence (assumed to be 0.5 due to lack of regional data), $q = 1 - p$ (0.5), and e is the margin of error (0.05). Substituting the values, the initial sample size was calculated to be 385. To account for a potential 10% non-response rate, an additional 40 participants were added, resulting in a final sample size of 425.

Inclusion and Exclusion criteria:

Students aged 15 to 28 years from schools, colleges, and universities on the Peshawar University campus have been included in a cross-sectional survey. Students who had any physical/mental impairment or those who didn't give consent have been excluded.

Data collection procedure:

A structured, self-administered questionnaire was used for data collection, comprising two sections. Section A covered demographic details, including name (optional), gender, age, marital status, contact (optional), and institutional affiliation. Section B focused on the identification of allergic conditions through 14 close-ended symptom-based questions with "Yes" or "No" responses. These items assessed previous diagnoses, self-perceived allergies, use of anti-allergic medications, family history, and the presence of common allergic symptoms such as sneezing, itching, wheezing, and reactions to cosmetics, food, pets, plants, and environmental triggers like dust mites and seasonal changes. The questionnaire was designed after an extensive literature search. The questionnaire was presented and subsequently approved by the Community Medicine and Medical Education Department of Khyber Medical College and the Medicine and ENT Department of Khyber Teaching Hospital. A pilot study with 30 participants was conducted, and it

yielded significant results. Based on the findings, slight changes were made to the questionnaire. After these revisions, the questionnaire was used for the rest of the study [9].

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION:

The study was approved by IREB Khyber Medical College under reference number 571/IREB/KMC.

Results:

Table 1: Distribution of self-reported allergy types by gender.

Table 1 presents the distribution of self-reported types of allergies among male and female participants (n = 425), comprising 230 males and 195 females. Dust allergy was the most frequently reported in both genders, with a slightly higher proportion among females (60.78%) compared to males (52.79%), though this difference was not statistically

significant (p = 0.08). Seasonal allergies were more common among females (36.21%) than males (28.43%), and the difference reached statistical significance (p = 0.04). Pollen allergy showed a significantly higher prevalence among males (28.93%) than females (18.97%) (p = 0.01). Similarly, contact dermatitis was more commonly reported by females (40.09%) compared to males (31.47%) and was also statistically significant (p = 0.041). Other types of allergies, including allergic rhinitis, conjunctivitis, cosmetic, food, plant, and animal allergies, showed no statistically significant gender differences. These findings suggest that while certain types of allergies are more frequently reported by one gender, particularly seasonal and contact allergies in females and pollen allergy in males, most differences were not statistically significant, indicating a relatively similar pattern of self-reported allergic conditions across genders.

Table 1: Distribution of self-reported allergy types by gender.

Type of allergy	Male (n%)	Female (n%)	Total	p-value (chi-square test)
Dust	121 (52.79%)	118 (60.78%)	239(56.2%)	0.08
Allergic rhinitis	91 (39.59%)	86 (43.97%)	177(41.64%)	0.36
Allergic conjunctivitis	72 (31.47%)	62 (32%)	134(31.52%)	0.91
Seasonal	65 (28.43%)	70 (36.21%)	135(31.76%)	0.04*
Pollen	66 (28.93%)	37 (18.97%)	103(24.2%)	0.01*
Contact dermatitis	72 (31.47%)	78 (40.09%)	150 (35.29%)	0.041*
Cosmetic	48 (20.81%)	69 (35.59%)	117(27.52%)	0.08
Plants	41 (17.77%)	48 (24.59%)	89(20.9%)	0.07
Food	53 (23.35%)	36 (18.53%)	89(20.9%)	0.21
Animals	37 (16.24%)	30 (15.56%)	67(15.7%)	0.32

Table 2: Distribution of self-reported positive family history of various allergy types by gender.

Table 2 presents the distribution of self-reported positive family history of various types of allergies among 240 participants (55.71% of the total sample) who indicated a familial predisposition to allergic conditions. A comparison between males and females was conducted using the chi-square test. The most commonly reported familial allergy was allergic conjunctivitis, with 29.0% of females and 17.8% of males reporting a positive family history; this difference was statistically significant (p = 0.01). Similarly, pollen allergy had a significantly higher family history reported by females (6.0%) compared to males (2.0%) (p = 0.04). Other allergy types, such as allergic rhinitis, cosmetic allergy, food allergy, and contact dermatitis, showed varying frequencies between genders but did not reach statistical significance (p > 0.05). For example, 16.4% of females vs. 10.0% of males reported a family history of allergic rhinitis (p = 0.09), and cosmetic allergy was more frequent in males (5.6%) than females (3.0%), but also not significant (p = 0.15).

These findings suggest that certain allergic conditions—particularly allergic conjunctivitis and pollen allergy—may have a stronger familial component in females than males within this sample.

Table 2: Distribution of self-reported positive family history of various allergy types by gender.

Types of allergy	Male (n%)	Female (n%)	Total 240 (55.71%)	P value (chi-square)
Dust	19(7.9%)	8 (3.3%)	27 (11.2%)	0.78
Allergic rhinitis	23 (9.5%)	32 (13.3%)	55 (22.8%)	0.09
Allergic conjunctivitis	41 (17%)	57 (23.7%)	71 (40.7%)	0.01*
Seasonal	5 (2%)	6 (2.5%)	11 (4.5%)	0.72
Pollen	5 (2%)	12 (5%)	17 (7%)	0.04*
Contact dermatitis	9 (3.75%)	8 (3.33%)	19 (7.08%)	0.99
Cosmetic	13 (5.4%)	6 (2.5%)	19 (7.9%)	0.15
Plants	2 (0.8%)	7 (2.9%)	9 (3.7%)	0.07
Food	5 (2%)	2 (0.8%)	7 (2.8%)	0.45
Animals	2 (0.8%)	3 (1.5%)	5 (2.3%)	0.50

Table 3: Distribution of physician-diagnosed allergy types by gender.

Table 3 summarises the distribution of physician-diagnosed allergies among participants who self-reported a confirmed diagnosis 181/425(42.5%), with 81 (44.7%) males and 100(55.2%) females. The most frequently reported physician-diagnosed allergy was dust mite allergy, affecting (27.6%) of participants, with a nearly equal distribution among males (23) and females (27), and no statistically significant gender difference ($p = 0.92$). Atopic dermatitis and cosmetic allergy showed statistically significant gender differences. Atopic dermatitis was more frequently reported among females (12 cases) than males (10 cases), with a p-value of 0.037, indicating a significant association. Cosmetic

allergy was reported significantly more by females (10 cases) than males (3 cases), with a p-value of <0.001 , suggesting a strong gender-related difference. Other allergies, such as allergic rhinitis, food, animal, and plant allergies, seasonal allergy, conjunctivitis, and pollen allergy, showed no statistically significant differences between genders ($p > 0.05$). Overall, there was a statistically significant difference in the total number of diagnosed allergies between males and females ($p < 0.001$), indicating a higher burden of confirmed allergies among females in this sample.

Table 3: Distribution of physician-diagnosed allergy types by gender.

Type of Allergy	Male (n)	Female (n)	Total (n)	p-value(chi-square)
Dust mites	23 (28.3%)	27 (27%)	50 (27.6%)	0.92
Allergic rhinitis	13 (16%)	15 (15%)	28 (15.4%)	0.338
Atopic dermatitis	10 (12%)	12 (12%)	22 (12.10%)	0.037*
Seasonal allergy	8 (9.8%)	10 (10%)	18 (9.9%)	0.98
Allergic conjunctivitis	6 (7.4%)	9 (9%)	15 (8.2%)	0.73
Cosmetic allergy	3 (3.7%)	10 (10%)	13 (7.10%)	<0.001*
Pollen allergy	5 (6%)	6 (6%)	11 (6.07%)	0.24
Plant allergy	4 (4.9%)	5 (5%)	9 (4.97%)	0.89

Food allergy	4(4.9%)	4 (4%)	8 (4.40%)	0.984
Animal allergy	5 (6%)	2 (2%)	7 (3.86%)	0.791
Total	81(44.7%)	100(55.2%)	181/425(42.5%)	<0.001*

Discussion:

According to the findings of this study, 42.5% of participants (55.2% females and 44.7% males) reported being diagnosed with an allergy by a healthcare professional. This prevalence is higher than that reported in a study conducted in Saudi Arabia, where the rate was 36.2% [10]. The higher prevalence among females observed in this study is consistent with findings from a survey in Ajman, UAE, which reported that 73% of diagnosed allergy cases were female, compared to 27% male [11]. A total of 50.81% (31% female and 19.81% male) individuals reported having used anti-allergic medication at different times throughout their lives. For instance, international studies have also pointed to an increase in allergy frequency and a respective increase in anti-allergic prescriptions for all types of allergies [12].

In this study, approximately 240 (55.71%) of individuals reported having close relatives with allergies, suggesting a strong association between family history and the likelihood of developing allergic conditions. Supporting this, another study indicates that individuals with a family history of allergies are 3.3 times more likely to develop allergies themselves [13].

Seasonal allergies, in a higher proportion in females (36.21%) compared to males (28.43%). In comparison, a study conducted in the United States reported a 25.7% prevalence of seasonal allergies in males [14].

Pollen exposure was identified as a significant contributor to allergic symptoms such as red eyes, sneezing, and a runny nose. A total of 103 students (24.2% of 425) reported developing these symptoms upon exposure to pollens. The prevalence was slightly higher in males (28.93%) than in females (18.97%). Similarly, a study from China found that the prevalence of Pollen-Induced Allergic Rhinitis (PIAR) was 18.5%, with a greater frequency in males [15].

The prevalence of cosmetic-related allergies was found to be 27.52%, occurring more frequently in females (35.59%) than in males (20.81%). A UK-

based epidemiological survey reported that 36.8% of individuals—23% females and 13.8% males—experienced adverse reactions to personal care products, including perfumes, deodorants, hair products, face foundations, and nail cosmetics [16].

Plant-related allergies were reported by 20.9% of participants, including 24.59% of females and 17.77% of males. In contrast, a study utilising skin prick testing with a general allergen panel found a higher prevalence of 31.1% for plant-related allergies [17].

Food allergies affected approximately 89 respondents (20.91%), with a slightly higher distribution among males (23.35%) than among females (18.53%). Another study reported a total food allergy prevalence of 13%, including 5% in adults and 8% in children [18].

Animal-related allergies were present in 15.76% of the sample, with nearly equal rates in males (16.24%) and females (15.56%). Cats were identified as the most common source of pet-related allergies. Supporting this, a study reported that 14% of individuals either removed pets from their homes (12%) or avoided owning pets altogether due to allergy symptoms (2%) [19].

Dust mites were identified as the most common allergen in this population, with a prevalence of 56.2%. This type of allergy was more prevalent in females (60.78%) than in males (52.79%). A study from the Islamabad Allergy and Asthma Centre using skin prick tests reported an even higher prevalence of 81.7% for dust mite allergies [20].

The frequency of allergic conjunctivitis, allergic dermatitis, and allergic rhinitis was recorded at 31.52%, 35.29%, and 41.64%, respectively. A large proportion of participants experienced multiple coexisting allergic conditions, with conjunctivitis co-occurring with rhinitis being the most frequent combination. A cross-sectional study conducted in Karachi reported a lower prevalence of allergic conjunctivitis at 19.2%, with boys being more affected than girls, which differs from the findings of this study [21]. Another study using skin prick testing

across Pakistan identified allergic rhinitis as the most common allergic condition, with a prevalence of

Conclusion:

This study highlights the high frequency of different types of allergies among students of Peshawar University, emphasising the need for comprehensive preventive measures and management strategies. Students being most prone to the environment and its hazards provide a complete picture of Allergy. Implementing appropriate measures, such as allergen identification and its management, would help reduce the frequency. Awareness campaigns should be conducted, and appropriate counselling the overall health and well-being of the students can be improved, leading to better academic and life outcomes.

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